

INVESTIGATION FOR POWER OVER FIBER IMPACT ON GIGABIT DATA TRANSMISSION IN SI-POF

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Abstract: We present experimental and theoretical results on the influence of the power-over-fiber signal (PoF) on the data traffic signal-to-noise ratio when transmitted simultaneously into SI-POF. We also discuss the potential of PoF to optically powering multiple sensors in specific applications like IoT.

Key words: SI-POF, Power over Fiber, Gigabit Transmission, Home Network, Sensor Network.

1. Introduction

Large core step index (SI) plastic optical fiber (POF) is considered to be very useful in many applications such as home networking [1] due to many advantages such as easy installation and high bending tolerance. Today, short-reach network data transmission at Gbit/s rates is more requested by users due to the growth of different multimedia end-user services like high definition TV or IPTV. On the other hand, Power-over-fiber (PoF) technology has been proposed to feed some elements in the access network portion as well as to supply energy to wireless access points (AP) that are used to process RF signals in multi services systems [2]. PoF usually consists of a high power laser diode (HPLD), an optical fiber and a photovoltaic cell (PV). PoF technology utilizing different kinds of multimode fibers capable of delivering hundreds of mW to the remote node is shown in [3]. An analysis of the impact of the high optical PoF power levels with simultaneous data signal transmission then becomes of prime importance [4]. On the other hand, this technology is promising in environments with high electromagnetic interference like smart IoT solutions to remotely feeding sensors [5].

Hence in this work we analyze the impact of PoF signals in coexistence with data transmission over a SI-POF link. The PoF system efficiency over the SI-POF link is also addressed.

2. Experimental set-up

Fig.1 (a) shows a schematic of the experimental setup. The setup is based on a PC equipped with a 1 Gigabit Ethernet interface in combination with a Media Converter (MC) used to generate and to read the transmitted data bits [6]. The MC converts the Gigabit Ethernet frames into a 16-level Pulse Amplitude Modulation (PAM) signal (named Tx-signal), and vice versa. At the transmitter side, the Tx-signal is used to modulate the laser diode (LD) of the data channel at 650nm. The PoF signal is based on a LD emitting at 405nm. Data and power channels are multiplexed and launched into a 10m-long SI-POF link through a MUX device which is based on reflective diffraction grating technology with low insertion losses ILs ~ 4.5 dB. At the reception stage the received optical signal is converted back into electrical domain by a PIN photodiode (PD) included in the MC.

3. Results and Discussion

Fig.1 (b,c) shows the effect of PoF signal on the data traffic signal-to-noise ratio (SNR). It is clearly seen that SNR degrades linearly while increasing the PoF signal. Theoretical calculations emulating the experimental parameters agreed with the experimental results in terms of tendency. These calculations showed that the relative intensity noise (RIN) of the PoF signal provides the highest impact on the degradation of the SNR. As mentioned before POF nowadays is used in many automation and home networks. The potential of PoF technology in these networks is interesting thus providing advantages over other powering technologies like immunity to electromagnetic interference. We following analyze the possibility of utilizing PoF systems to remotely feed sensor nodes in smart IoT solutions where the maximum number of nodes that can be fed depends on the maximum power that can be delivered to these nodes. This power depends on many factors like transmission loss and the damage power density threshold which is around 6.6 KW/cm^2 in plastic optical fibers. Depending on the photovoltaic cell (PV) efficiency, Att. and Mux/Demux losses (integrated from [7]) we showed the system energy efficiency (SEE) at different wavelengths. We also show how this efficiency can be improved with Mux/Demux losses $\sim 1\text{dB}$ or by using different powering architecture (shared or dedicated) specifically for our proposed PoF channel. The electrical power at the remote side P_{elec} ($\sim 250\mu\text{W}$ and 1.5mW for shared and dedicated scenarios

respectively) for the proposed system can be enough for powering multiple sensors with low power consumption as shown in Table 1. These sensors can be used in this type of networks for smart home automation.

Fig.1: (a) Schematic of the experimental setup. Normalized calculated and measured SNR of the data signal vs. PoF signal delivered. Data signal power: (b) -8 dBm (c) -12dBm.

TABLE 1: Sensors Specifications

Device	Type	Power Consumption (μ W)
HTS221 / LPS33HW	Temperature and Humidity / Pressure	7.2 / 21.6

Fig.2: System energy efficiency (SEE) for the PoF link: (a) LD Pin=40mW, Mux/Demux IL~1dB, (b) Our proposed system (shared scenario), (c) Shared and dedicated power scenario for our proposed PoF channel.

4. Conclusions

A 1 Gbit/s real time 10m-long SI-POF link of BER $< 1 \times 10^{-10}$ in coexistence with a PoF signal has been implemented. This system can support future in-home network deployments as part of a broadband access network with the possibility of remote feeding capabilities. We have showed that 1mW of electrical power (P_{elec}) can be delivered at the remote side with our system by using a LD@405nm with input optical power of 40 mW and a PV cell with efficiency of 25%.

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